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Departmental Innovation Index for Colombia: a tool to guide STI policies in territories¹

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Introduction

Innovation is key to increase competitiveness, development, and life quality; this is not only limited to business or institutional capabilities or results but is also related with other macroeconomic or general welfare variables (Akman & Yilmaz, 2008; Rajapathirana & Hui, 2018). Therefore, its measurement through robust instruments is a key element to focalize, implement, and evaluate public (and private) policies to promote it (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000; Loray, 2017).

The measurement of innovation, both at the micro (company) and macro/meso levels, is fundamental for the agents involved in the industry, as well as for policymakers and scholars. For this reason, when analyzing the literature on the measurement of innovation, a diversity of approaches, prescriptions and practices are found (Adams, Bessant & Phelps, 2006; Dziallas & Blind, 2018), which have evolved from even the beginnings of the perspective Schumpeterian approach to innovation, to the consolidated systematization of guidelines and measurement concepts such as the Oslo Manual (OECD & Eurostat, 2018) or the Frascati Manual (OECD, 2015).

Consequently, for several years, most innovation metrics developed allow establishing a comparison parameter between different sectors and territories, particularly countries. The first measurement exercises compared research and development (R&D) spending, the number of patents and scientific publications (Godin, 2002; Smith, 2005). However, these indicators did not speak of innovation results, but rather of inputs and intermediate results, or processes prior to innovation *per se*.

Afterward, under the concept of Innovation Systems (Freeman, 1987; Lundvall, 1992; Nelson, 1993; Edquist, 1997), literature began to study how different actors interacted and related

¹ This work was supported by National Planning Department and Colombian Observatory of Science and Technology.

among them to innovate, according to certain conditions or institutional backgrounds of certain territories. By considering different agents involved in innovation processes, some territories achieved greater impacts from innovation instruments and policies, as well as better resource allocation and decision-making (World Bank, 2014; IDB, 2014).

The process of understanding and innovation measurement has evolved and strengthened since then. According to Hollanders & Van Cruysen (2009), there has been an increase in the number of innovation indicators, mainly for European countries and for comparative purposes, due to the availability of new statistical operations that collect data on the innovative performance of firms, regions, and countries. These indicators are used to build composite indicators². Some of the firsts and best-known composite indicators correspond to the Science, Technology, and Industry Scoreboard (OECD, 2007), the Global Competitiveness Report (World Economic Forum, 2008), the Innovation Score Board (European Commission - DG Enterprise and Industry, 2010) and the Global Innovation Index (Cornell University, INSEAD, & WIPO, 2008).

Hence, since recognizing the importance of measuring innovation for Colombia and its departments³, in 2015 Colombia's Government identified the need of having a composite indicator for the country and its departments. The main interest was to have an index that would allow each agent of the National Innovation System to have relevant information to make better decisions, design efficient strategies and measure the evolution of innovation in Colombia. In addition, to have a comparability mechanism in terms of innovation at the sub-national level.

Therefore, this document presents the conceptualization and construction process of the *Departmental Innovation Index for Colombia (IDIC - by its acronym in Spanish)* based on a methodological structure adaptation of the Global Innovation Index (GII). This document is made up of four sections: The first one presents the conceptual framework and the general characteristics of the IDIC; The second section describes the methodological steps developed for its construction. The third section highlights the main results of the latest IDIC measurement; and the fourth section present how the IDIC components contribute to make it a tool for the design of STI policies.

The Departmental Innovation Index for Colombia - IDIC

The Departmental Innovation Index for Colombia is derived from the adaptation of the Global Innovation Index (GII). The GII was released in 2007 by the Cornell University, the European Institute of Business Administration (INSEAD), and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). The objectives of this report consist of measuring the multidimensional aspects of innovation that exists in an economy to trace routes for public policy makers in terms of innovation, focus resources, evaluate impact, and trace the evolution of progress of each country included in the index, in topics related to innovation.

The IDIC incorporates the same conceptual framework of the GII, and it's based on a broad and systemic vision of innovation, in which the national innovation systems transform the *Inputs* into Innovation Results (*Outputs*), which allows the measurement of the multidimensional facets of innovation. Thus, it provides insights that can help in the adaptation of policies to promote long-term growth, productivity improvement and employment growth

² In some cases, indices.

³ Equivalent of states and/or provinces in Colombia's administrative division.

(DNP, OCyT & C230, 2016). However, the IDIC is unique in the composition of its indicators and guarantees the relevance, continuity, and scope of each of them in the Colombian context.⁴

One of the advantages of the IDIC is that, unlike other indices that measure innovation (nationally and internationally), it focuses on elements of innovation that go beyond evaluating the performance of the scientific and technological sector of the territories, which allows a broader assessment of the systemic conditions that determine innovation capabilities. Thus, this index is concerned with understanding the role of geographic proximity in inter-organizational learning processes and the role of local institutions in the articulation of innovation with territorial competitiveness (DNP, OCyT & C230, 2016).

The IDIC presents a systemic innovation measurement structure, which conceptualizes and approximates measures to the functioning of regional innovation systems (RIS) of each department (provinces) through theoretical constructs (pillars): (i) *Institutions*, measures the performance of institutional regulation of a territory, (ii) *Human Capital and Research*, seeks to estimate the functioning and quality of educational and research systems, (iii) *Infrastructure*, studies the mechanisms that facilitate the production and exchange of ideas, goods, and services; and (iv) and (v) *Markets and Businesses Sophistication*, estimates the proper development of production processes, entrepreneurship, and integration with other agents of the RIS.

Likewise, by incorporating the systemic understanding of innovation, these enabling factors of innovation are transformed into innovation results, or *Outputs*, which can be technological, knowledge, orange economy or creative goods and services. These *Outputs* are reflected in the IDIC in the pillars of: (vi) *Knowledge and Technology Production* and (vii) *Creative Production*.

IDIC construction methodology

The IDIC construction methodology is based on the parameters proposed by the OECD (2008) in its manual for composite indicators and on the methodology used in 2014 for the construction of the GII. The methodology and current conditions for measuring the IDIC in its 2021 version are described below.

- Composite measures and weights

As can be seen in Figure 1, the IDIC is made up of *Inputs* and *Results* sub-indices, which are built from the aggregation of pillars, which, at the same time, are divided into sub-pillars, and these are made up of composite or simple indicators (the minimum level of aggregation). The aggregation of each of these constructs is calculated from the simple average of each of the elements that compose it; in other words, within the index aggregation process no differential weights are assigned.

Therefore, the *Inputs* sub-index is obtained by applying the simple average of the pillars of *Institutions*, *Human Capital and Research*, *Infrastructure*, *Market Sophistication* and *Business Sophistication*. While the *Results* sub-index is calculated as the average of the scores achieved in the *Knowledge and Technology Production* and *Creative Production* pillars.

⁴ Although the first GII was released in 2007, the IDIC was adapted from the 2014 version.

Figure 1. IDIC structure

Source: Author's own elaboration.

- *Indicators*

IDIC's indicators are selected from the GII based on an exercise of relevance and adaptability to Colombia's data sources and availability. Its structure is composed by 109 univariate data, of which 4 are soft⁵ data and 105 hard data. These are aggregated to make up the 78 main indicators, of which 65 are univariate indicators and the rest are composite, calculated with the simple average of the sub-indicators that compose them.

- *Data standardization*

Data standardization is carried out to bring all the indicators to the same scale (0-100) and thus make the data comparable. For this, the *min-max method* of data re-scaling is used, while maintaining the positioning of the departments and their relative distances, as follows:

$$Y_n = \left(\frac{Y_{max} - Y_i}{Y_{max} - Y_{min}} \right) * 100$$

Where:

- Y_i : Original value
- Y_{max} : The maximum value
- Y_{min} : The minimum value
- Y_n : Normalized value

- *Missing values treatment*

For the treatment of missing values, the IDIC uses a principal components analysis (PCA) model to estimate them. The PCA takes the most important indicators of the same subpillar and with these predicts the missing values. This estimation is made groupings indicators by

⁵ Refers to data collected from perception surveys, for example, The Survey of Coexistence and Citizen Security.

subpillars with the purpose of performing the imputation with data are more related (conceptually) to the missing values.

- *Outliers treatment*

Outliers correspond to data that are 90% away from the mean of the indicator. For its identification, the boxplot method is used, in which it's possible to visually identify which atypical values are found within the distribution of the indicator, later a *winsorization* process is carried out to smooth the distribution, and thus to eliminate outliers.

- *IDIC performance clusters*

To generate the clusters of departments by IDIC performance, Ward's Minimum Variance Clustering technique is used for each of the indicators, through a hierarchical agglomerative grouping, having an objective function for minimizing variance of these groups. The similarity criterion proposed by this method consists of identifying pairs of groups that are closest to each other and then, in successive stages, forming new groupings, so that the increase in variance is as small as possible within the groups that it's forming.

These groupings consolidate the departments into 5 groups according to their performance: high, medium-high, medium, medium-low, and low, which reflect their level of innovation capabilities.

- *Indicators statistical consistency*

To validate the statistical coherence of the structure of the pillars and subpillars that compose the IDC, other PCA is performed to verify that the structure of each pillar and subpillar can explain at least 70 percent of the variance, The objective of this step is to ensure the IDIC structures explain the behavior that occurs in each of the constructs defined in terms of the interest of public policy makers.

Some results of the latest IDIC update

The main results of the measurement for 2021 are presented below. The map shows the IDIC department's performance, sorted by colors (performance clusters). The table on the right indicates the score and position for all departments.

Figure 2. IDIC 2021 results

Source: IDIC 2021.

In short, main results show:

- At a national level, IDIC 2021 has an average of 31.09 points. The first position of the general ranking is obtained by the Bogotá – Cundinamarca region with a score of 77.8. While, in the last position is the department of Vichada with a score of 11.83.
- The Bogotá – Cundinamarca region and the department of Antioquia continue to be the only two territories in the country that achieve a High performance (cluster) in the IDIC 2021 with an average score of 69.66. Therefore, Antioquia achieved a score of 61.43, a difference of 16.45 points from Bogotá – Cundinamarca.
- The Medium-High performance cluster is made up of 7 departments with an average score of 45.92 points. The group is headed by the department of Valle del Cauca with a score of 51.04, followed by Santander with a difference of 1.43 points with a score of 49.61. The performance group closes with the department of Bolívar with a score of 39.71 and the 9th position.

- IDIC 2021 presents 4 departments in the Medium performance cluster, with an average score of 34.47. The department of Boyacá leads this cluster with a score of 36.42, slightly surpassing the departments of Tolima and San Andrés y Providencia. The last department of this group is Cauca, with the 13th position and 31.98 points.
- The Medium-Low performance cluster has a total of 10 departments and has the largest number of territories; the average score for this group is 24.78. The best department in the Medium-Low performance group is Huila with a score of 27.97, however, it surpasses the departments of Norte de Santander, Meta, and Magdalena by a small difference. Finally, Amazonas is the last department in this group, with a score of 20.52.
- The 9 departments that had the lowest scores in the overall IDIC 2021 score represent the Low performance cluster with an average of 16.48. The department with the highest score in this cluster is Putumayo with 19.09 points. Finally, the ranking is closed by the department of Vichada with a score of 11.83. The important gap between the region of Bogotá - Cundinamarca and Vichada (66.05 points) evidences the unclosed gap between the Colombian territories in terms of innovation.

The IDIC as a tool to guide STI policies

The structure the IDIC propose allows innovation to be understood as a set of interactions, conditions, and knowledge flows among all the actors involved in Colombian RIS, and not as a linear process where there is an ideal to which all departments should aspire. Therefore, one of its advantages lies in its robustness to identify the way in which the different conditions that determine and promote innovation interact, opening the possibility for each department to generate differentiated systemic conditions with an objective to develop their own capabilities for generating and promoting innovation, and knowledge appropriation (DNP, OCyT & C230, 2016).

The IDIC's territorial scope makes possible to identify good practices and facilitates directing the design of policies, instruments, and programs to the conditions of each department, and those dimensions that may be hindering their performance in terms of innovation. Since the IDIC's conceptual design, its periodic updating has been considered to favor the follow-up and evaluation of the initiatives that are developed in each of the territories to promote science, technology, and innovation. In addition, it has been determined that for each new measurement it is necessary to review and modify (if needed) its indicators. These changes must obey both departmental and sectoral dynamics, as well as the consolidation of new data collection processes.

Besides the measurement and updating of the IDIC, a toolbox is generated for policymakers; this tool seeks to provide technical guidance to territorial entities for the design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of public policy on STI. The toolbox compiles a series of recommendations based on references from the literature, evidence-based analysis, and case studies, which allows departments to identify, adapt and replicate good practices in the design of STI policies. The toolbox proposes actions for each of the pillars and sub-pillars, according to IDIC's five performance clusters.

To complement the toolbox and to support the design of STI efficient policies and to evaluate the effects that a policy or a set of policies would have on the performance of the territories, a simulator of results was created and updated with each new version. This consists of a web app that containing the IDIC results that allows micro-simulation exercises to quantify the variations in the levels of innovation of the departments in the face of different probable

scenarios subject to changes in public policies according to the pillars and sub-pillars that make up the IDIC.

Synthesizing the points above mentioned, the IDIC is a key tool for policy makers through i) the information it provides on the state of innovation in territories, ii) the public policy recommendations related to the performance groups for pillars and subpillars, and iii) the possibility of simulating future scenarios depending on the implementation of changes or new public policy instruments.

Conclusions

Colombia's adaptation of the IDIC based on the GII is the first step toward an adequate innovation system dynamic measurement in the country since it is the first instrument that allows evaluating the impact of public innovation policies at the aggregate level and by departments. Additionally, it provides a good overview of trends in innovation over the last 5 years (the time horizon in which the IDIC has been calculated) and makes it possible to highlight the strengths and weaknesses of each department to focus resources or maintain good practices.

Another benefit of this index is that it allows identifying regional gaps in terms of innovation capabilities, as well as challenges and strengths. Therefore, the index is projected as an instrument that provides solid information based on representative data at the departmental level that allows public policy makers to focus actions to improve innovation capacities and results in their territories.

Finally, the IDIC provides information that, together with the toolbox and the simulator, allows policymakers to design science, technology, and innovation policies that favor their development, considering the capacities, strengths, and weaknesses of the territories. Consequently, the IDIC is a key input, which collects specific characteristics of the departments and allows the design of instruments, plans, programs, projects, and *ad hoc* policies.

References

- Adams, R., Bessant, J., & Phelps, R. (2006). Innovation management measurement: A review. *International journal of management reviews*, 8(1), 21-47.
- Akman, G., & Yilmaz, C. (2008). Innovative capability, innovation strategy and market orientation: an empirical analysis in Turkish software industry. *International journal of innovation management*, 12(01), 69-111.
- Banco Mundial. (2014). *Assessing Public Expenditures on Science, Technology, and Innovation*. Washington: Banco Mundial.
- BID (Banco Interamericano de Desarrollo). (2014). *¿Cómo repensar el desarrollo productivo? Políticas e instituciones sólidas para la transformación económica*. Washington: BID.
- Cornell University, INSEAD, & WIPO (2008). *The Global Innovation Index 2007*. Ithaca, Fontainebleau, and Geneva.
- DNP, OCyT & C230. (2016). *Índice Departamental de Innovación para Colombia (IDIC), 2015*. Bogotá: Departamento Nacional de Planeación.

Dutta, S., Lanvin, B., & Wunsch-Vincent, S. (Eds.). (2017). *Global Innovation Index 2017*. Cornell University.

Dziallas, M., & Blind, K. (2018). Innovation indicators throughout the innovation process: An extensive literature analysis. *Technovation*, 80, 3-29. doi:10.1016/j.technovation.2018.05.005

Hollanders, H. (2009). Measuring innovation: The European innovation scoreboard. *Measuring creativity. European Commission Joint Research Centre Luxembourg*, 27-40.

Edquist, C. (1997). *Systems of Innovation: Technologies, Institutions and Organizations*. Londres: Printer Publishers, Cassell Academic.

Etzkowitz, H., & Leydesdorff, L. (2000). The dynamics of innovation: from National Systems and “Mode 2” to a Triple Helix of university–industry–government relations. *Research policy*, 29(2), 109-123.

European Commission - DG Enterprise and Industry (2010). European Innovation Scoreboard 2009. Available in: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/content/european-innovation-scoreboard-2009-0_en

Foro Económico Mundial (2008). The Global Competitiveness Report 2008-2009. Available in: <https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-competitiveness-report-2008-2009>

Freeman, C. (1987). *Technology policy and economic performance: Lessons from Japan*. Londres: Pinter Pub Ltd.

Godin, B. (2002). The rise of innovation surveys: Measuring a fuzzy concept. *Canadian Science and Innovation Indicators Consortium, project on the History and Sociology of S&T Statistics*. Retrieved from http://www.csiic.ca/PDF/Godin_16.pdf

Hollanders, H., & Van Cruysen, A. (2009). Design, creativity and innovation: A scoreboard approach. *Innovation*.

Iisuka, M. & Hollanders, H. (2017). The need to customise innovation indicators in developing countries. *UNU-MERIT Working Papers*. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Michiko-Iizuka/publication/319059600_The_need_to_customise_innovation_indicators_in_developing_countries_Indicators_in_Developing_Countries/links/598d9f77a6fdcc58acc01a45/The-need-to-customise-innovation-indicators-in-developing-countries-Indicators-in-Developing-Countries.pdf

Loray, R. (2017). Políticas públicas en ciencia, tecnología e Innovación. *Revista de Estudios Sociales* (pp. 68-70). DOI. 10.7440/res62.2017.07.

Lundvall, B.-A. (1992). *National systems of innovation: Towards a theory innovation and interactive learnings*. Londres: Pinter Publishers.

Nelson, R. (1993). *National Systems of Innovation: A comparative study*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

OECD (2007), *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Scoreboard 2007*, OECD Publishing, Paris, https://doi.org/10.1787/sti_scoreboard-2007-en.

OECD/Eurostat (2018), *Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation, 4th Edition*, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris/Eurostat, Luxembourg, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304604-en>.

OCDE (2015), *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development*, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities. Publicado por acuerdo con la OCDE, París (Francia). DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>

Rajapathirana, R. P. J., & Hui, Y. (2018). Relationship between innovation capability, innovation type, and firm performance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 3(1), 44–55. doi:10.1016/j.jik.2017.06.002

Smith. (2005). Measuring Innovation. (M. A. Fagerberg, Ed.) *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation*, 148-177.